

${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ transitions, respectively suggestive of a spin free octahedral configuration of these compounds in agreement with the magnetic moment data. Nickel complexes give rise to three absorption bands at 10.0 (4), 15.8 (6) and 28.5 (300) kK regions assignable⁵ to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively indicating an octahedral stereochemistry. In case of copper(II) chelate two bands are observed at 18.0 and 14.8 kK regions whereas in the case of the base adducts only a single band is observed at 15.3-15.5 kK with an increase in the value of the molar absorptivity. The disappearance of the former band, the increase in the intensity and the clear isobestic point confirm that only two species are involved. On the basis of many analogous observations⁶⁻⁷ the copper complexes presumably are penta-coordinated.

On the basis of analysis, conductance and infrared spectral studies, zinc and cadmium complexes possibly are penta-coordinated as observed⁸ in the case of base adducts of *bis*-(acetylacetonato)zinc. In view of the spherical symmetry of this ion and in absence of crystal field effects penta-coordination is not quite unusual in these cases.

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Benzoyl Glycine by Peroxydisulphate

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KINETICS of oxidation of various organic and inorganic compounds by peroxydisulphate has been reviewed^{1,2}. The kinetic study on the oxida-

tion of some amino acids has been reported by Srivastava and Chandra³. Such a study may help in visualizing the role of amino acid derivatives in biological systems where they are likely to undergo oxidation reactions.

Experimental

Potassium peroxydisulphate (E. Merck, G.R.), benzoylglycine (B.D.H., A.R.), silver nitrate (B.D.H.) and all other chemicals used were of high purity. All the solutions were prepared in distilled water. The reaction at desired temperature was followed by estimating excess of peroxydisulphate by standard iodometric method of Szabo *et al*⁴ as modified by Khulbe and Srivastava⁵.

Product analysis :

Under the kinetic conditions, the final oxidation products of benzoylglycine were benzoic acid, formaldehyde and ammonia. Benzoic acid was detected by spotting the reaction mixture with bromophenol blue which gives yellow brown spot⁶. The aldehyde was characterized by preparing 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative⁷ in the presence of 0.005 M NaOH. Ammonia formed was detected by Nessler's reagent. The low yield of aldehyde indicates that it combines with the ammonia formed during the reaction. For the same reason formaldehyde is detected only in the presence of NaOH, because the latter facilitates the evolution of ammonia.

Results and Discussion

The reaction was found to follow first order rate law with respect to $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ at all concentrations. The velocity constant decreases slightly with increase in $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$, which is attributed to an increase in ionic strength or partly due to the formation of ion pairs⁸ [Table 1(a)]. The specific reaction rate remains almost the same at all concentrations of benzoylglycine, but is linearly related to silver ion concentration [Table 1(b) and (c)].

The salt effect is negative. The specific inhibitory effect of various cations followed the general order $K^+ > Na^+ > Li^+ > H^+$ depending upon charge size ratio⁹.

The reaction was studied at different temperatures ranging from 30 to 45° so as to calculate various energy parameters. The value of energy of activation, frequency factor, entropy of activation were found to be 13.72 k cal mole⁻¹, 1.62×10^6 sec⁻¹ and -41.18 e.u., respectively.

The SO_4^+ radical was detected¹⁰ by allyl acetate and esr spectroscopically. The formation of radicals NH_2-CH_2-COO and $\dot{C}H_2NH_2$ were proved by carrying out the polymerization with acrylonitrile. The white polymeric product analysed by ir spectra was found to contain amino and carboxy carbonyl groups. The generation of the above radicals have already been proved by Chandra and Srivastava³.

TABLE 1—THE EFFECT OF CHANGE IN (a) PEROXYDISULPHATE (b) BENZOYL GLYCINE (c) SILVER NITRATE ON VELOCITY CONSTANT AT 35°

(a) $[Ag^+] = 1 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[Benzoylglycine] = 0.005 M$	
$[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ M	$k \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
0.01	3.85
0.02	3.40
0.03	3.95
0.04	3.25
(b) $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 0.02 M$, $[Ag^+] = 1 \times 10^{-2} M$	
$[Benzoylglycine]$ M	$k \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
0.005	3.20
0.010	3.22
0.015	3.40
0.020	3.45
(c) $[Benzoylglycine] = 0.005 M$, $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 0.02 M$	
$[Ag^+] \times 10^2$ M	$k \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
0.5	1.74
1.0	3.40
2.0	6.76
2.5	8.46
3.0	10.35

The stoichiometry of the reaction is given by the equation

Mechanism :

The rate of oxidation of benzoylglycine ($k = 3.11 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$) is found to be identical to that of glycine ($k = 3.30 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$). This observation is in favour of the fact that the order with respect to the substrate is zero. The reaction is associated with low value of energy of activation indicating that the rate determining step must include the reaction between two oppositely charged ions¹¹. The catalytic activity of silver ion is due to the formation of higher valent silver ion. Energy of activation suggests electron transfer process^{1,2}. Taking into account above observations the following reaction mechanism has been proposed.

First two steps have been proposed by Bawn and Margerison¹⁸ and involve one electron release reaction with the formation of Ag(II), followed by the latter's reaction with water according to step (3). All other steps are similar to oxidation of glycine³.

Experimentally, the orders with respect to benzoylglycine is zero which suggests that the substrate is not involved in the rate determining step. So the rate expression may be given as,

$$\text{Rate} = k[S_2O_8^{2-}][Ag^+]$$

Thus, the oxidation of benzoylglycine may be considered to be a catalysed unimolecular reaction or pseudo-first order reaction¹⁴. The rate expression can be written as,

$$\text{Rate} = k'[S_2O_8^{2-}]$$

where $k' = k[Ag^+]$ is the first order rate constant.

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